

Peripheral inflammatory markers and emotional dysregulation in children and adolescents: a systematic review

Protocol version

Version 1.0 – January 2026

Background

Emotional dysregulation is a core transdiagnostic feature of child and adolescent psychopathology and is commonly operationalized through the Dysregulation Profile derived from the Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL). Increasing evidence suggests that immune system alterations and low-grade peripheral inflammation may contribute to emotional and behavioral dysregulation during neurodevelopment. Peripheral inflammatory markers, such as circulating cytokines and acute-phase proteins, represent accessible indicators of neuroimmune activation and have been investigated across a range of pediatric neurodevelopmental and psychiatric conditions. However, existing findings are heterogeneous and fragmented, and no systematic review has specifically synthesized evidence focusing on CBCL-derived emotional dysregulation indices in relation to peripheral inflammatory markers in pediatric populations.

Objectives

Primary objective

To systematically review and synthesize the available evidence on the association between peripheral inflammatory markers and emotional dysregulation, as assessed by the CBCL-derived Dysregulation Profile, in children and adolescents.

Secondary objectives

1. To examine whether specific classes of peripheral inflammatory markers (e.g., cytokines, acute-phase proteins) are consistently associated with emotional dysregulation.
2. To explore differences in these associations across clinical and community samples.
3. To assess the potential moderating role of age, sex, and diagnostic context.

Eligibility criteria

Population

Children and adolescents aged 0–18 years, from clinical or community-based samples.

Exposure

Peripheral inflammatory or immune-related biomarkers measured quantitatively from biological samples (e.g., blood or serum), including cytokines and acute-phase proteins.

Outcome

Emotional dysregulation assessed using the Child Behavior Checklist Dysregulation Profile or related CBCL-derived indices.

Study designs

Randomized and non-randomized studies, including cross-sectional, case–control, and cohort studies. Randomized controlled trials will be included if relevant biomarker data are reported.

Exclusion criteria

Case reports, small case series (<5 participants), reviews, editorials, conference abstracts without full text, animal or in vitro studies, and studies without quantitative peripheral inflammatory marker assessment.

Information sources and search strategy

Electronic searches will be conducted in PubMed/MEDLINE, Scopus, and Web of Science. Search terms will combine controlled vocabulary and free-text terms related to emotional dysregulation, Child Behavior Checklist, inflammation, cytokines, and pediatric populations. Reference lists of included studies will be hand-searched.

Study selection

Two reviewers will independently screen titles and abstracts, followed by full-text assessment of potentially eligible studies. Disagreements will be resolved by consensus or by a third reviewer.

Data extraction

Data will be extracted using a standardized form, including study characteristics, sample features, inflammatory markers assessed, CBCL-derived outcomes, and main findings.

Risk of bias assessment

Risk of bias will be assessed independently by two reviewers using appropriate tools according to study design (e.g., Newcastle–Ottawa Scale for observational studies).

Data synthesis

A narrative synthesis will be conducted. If data are sufficiently homogeneous, a quantitative synthesis may be considered. Study heterogeneity will be explored qualitatively, considering population characteristics, biomarkers, and study design.

Dissemination

Results will be submitted for publication in a peer-reviewed international journal and presented at relevant scientific conferences.